

An innovative solar-driven directly air-cooled LiBr–H₂O absorption chiller prototype for residential use

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Abstract

In this study were conducted on an innovative solar-driven, directly air-cooled, single effect, 4.5 kW-LiBr/H₂O absorption chiller prototype. The aim was to air-condition a 40-m² room located in Madrid. The solar facility consisted of a vacuum flat-plate collector field, with a total aperture area of 42.2 m², a 25-kW external plate heat exchanger and a 1.5-m³ storage tank. The paper reports the findings in detail, including solar cooling facility temperatures and thermal power, solar fraction, COP and SCOP values on a day when the outdoor dry bulb temperature ranged from 30 to 37.7 °C. The daily results for the entire trial are also given. No solution crystallization problems arose inside the prototype even when the generator feed temperature reached 109 °C. The lowest chilled water temperature attained was 14.3 °C, and the mean COP_{th} and SCOP values were 0.53 and 0.06, respectively. This study forms part of a larger project whose aim is to use solar power as a source of heat in air-cooled absorption chillers in residential buildings.

Keywords: Solar cooling, Absorption, Directly air-cooled, LiBr–H₂O, Single effect, Vacuum flat-plate collectors, experimental trials

1. Introduction

The scientific community's concern over energy consumption and GHG emissions has induced European authorities to adopt a series of measures in recent years. Hence, European Parliament adopted Directive 2002/91/CE on the energy performance of buildings to reduce energy consumption and CO₂ emissions. Among others, the directive deals with the increase in the number of mechanical compression air conditioning systems in southern European countries, with the concomitant daytime overloads on electricity systems, and the need to prioritise strategies that would improve the thermal performance of buildings in the summertime [1]. In 2008, European Parliament enacted legislation designed to reach a triple objective by 2020: a 20% reduction in CO₂ emissions, a 20% increase in energy efficiency and a 20% share of renewable energies in EU consumption. Further to that legislation, these goals should be met by encouraging the use of renewable energies in electric power, heating and cooling [2].

Absorption chillers are an example of technology that attempts to mitigate both the dependence on electric power, specifically during summertime overloads, and environmental problems [3]. On the one hand, as they have no mechanical compressor, these chillers can use residual heat or solar power as the source of energy and, on the other hand, their working fluid consists of solutions (such as NH₃–H₂O and LiBr–H₂O) that are environmentally innocuous. Single effect absorption chillers are less efficient in terms of primary energy than air-cooled mechanical compression chillers [4]. Consequently, they are not a viable solution when powered by commercial fuels. When driven by solar energy, however, they constitute an alternative worth exploring. Progress has recently been made in solar collector-powered absorption chillers on the back of efforts to protect

the environment and developments in new components and systems [5–12]. The primary advantage of solar-powered cooling facilities is that the cooling demand is highest when solar irradiance is most intense (summertime). The major problems encountered by such facilities include their dependence on environmental variables, such as outdoor temperature, solar irradiance and wind speed, along with their high initial cost. Solar cooling is not yet able to compete economically with conventional air-conditioning systems, because solar systems are more expensive to run than conventional mechanical compression facilities [6,13]. Nonetheless, when the facility is designed to be used both in the summer and the winter for space heating and solar domestic hot water (SDHW), these costs can be lowered [14].

In Spain, in 2006, the total medium and low temperature heat demand ($t < 250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) came to 258 TWh or 23% of the total. The use of heat for air conditioning in the service (8.6%) and residential (2.4%) sectors accounted for 11% of that demand [14]. In 2006, around 70 thermal solar air-conditioning facilities were in operation in Europe, most in Germany and Spain. Of that total, 59% had absorption chillers, 11% adsorption chillers and 23% were fitted with desiccant systems [15]. Sparber et al. [16] estimated total solar-powered cooling capacity to be on the order of 9 MW, with a total collector area of around 23,720 m^2 . Henning [15], based on information furnished by facilities actually operating with different applications and collectors, computed the specific collector area for absorption systems to be $2.5\text{ m}^2/\text{kW}$. According to the numerical simulations performed by Eicker and Pietruschka [17], an aperture area of $3\text{ m}^2/\text{kW}$ is needed to attain a solar fraction of 80% in Madrid if the generator operates at $80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The use of air-cooled absorption chillers, i.e., systems with no cooling tower, not only prevents legionellosis, but saves water, maintenance expense and space, key considerations for the residential sector. The drawback is that a special design is required to reduce component size [18]. The literature contains experimental results for water-cooled, solar-powered LiBr–H₂O absorption chillers [19–23]. Examples of solar-powered, air-cooled LiBr–H₂O absorption chiller facilities have also been described [24,25]. To the authors' knowledge, only two air-cooled LiBr–H₂O absorption chillers have ever been brought to market: a double effect, 35-kW machine with a nominal thermal COP of 0.85 [26], and a 4.5-kW single effect indirectly air-cooled chiller with a rated thermal COP of 0.67 [25]. Neither is presently available. That notwithstanding, the pursuit of a viable commercial air-cooled absorption chiller has not waned and research continues along those lines [27,28].

The present paper introduces an innovative, directly air-cooled absorber-condenser, low power, single effect LiBr–H₂O prototype absorption chiller driven by a solar-powered facility using vacuum flat-plate solar collectors. The prototype performance is assessed from the standpoint of the external fluids. In the first part of the paper, process temperatures, heat transfer rates and performances obtained in the facility during a hot day, with a maximum outside dry bulb temperature of $37.7\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, are discussed in depth. The second part reports a daily summary of the 10-day experimental trial conducted in the summer of 2009. The study forms part of a larger project whose goal is to use solar power as a source of heat in air-cooled absorption chillers in residential buildings.

2. Description of the solar-driven absorption cooling facility

The facility (Fig. 1) consisted of a solar thermal plant, a directly air-cooled single effect LiBr–H₂O absorption chiller prototype and a fan coil. The aim was to air condition a 40-m^2 room in a Heat Pump Laboratory owned by the Eduardo Torroja Institute for Construction Science (IETec – a Spanish National Research Council body), with an area of 80 m^2 and a total volume of 240 m^3 , located at Arganda del Rey, a town southeast of Madrid at latitude $40^{\circ}18'$. The comfort t_{in} was set at $23\text{--}25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the range laid down in the Spanish Regulations for Thermal Facilities in Buildings in effect in 2009 [29].

2.1. Solar thermal plant

The solar unit had three hydraulic circuits, whose main components are listed below.

- The *primary circuit* comprised 24 vacuum flat-plate solar collectors with a total aperture area of 42.2 m^2 . According to the manufacturer, the collectors had an optical efficiency of 0.81, a first order heat loss coefficient of $2.61\text{ W/m}^2\text{ K}$ and a second order heat loss coefficient of $0.008\text{ W/m}^2\text{ K}^2$. The collectors, which were tilted on a 30° angle over the horizontal, were arranged in four groups of six,

facing south. The thermal fluid was a 30% ethylenglycol solution in water, and the nominal flow rate was $m_{\text{fcol}} = 0.47 \text{ kg/s}$. A 295-W pump (P_1) drove the thermal fluid through the solar collectors and then to the hot side of a 25-kW plate heat exchanger (PHE), insulated from the exterior with a 30- mm thick polyethylene membrane. In the PHE, the primary circuit thermal fluid transferred heat to the secondary circuit thermal fluid.

- The *secondary circuit* consisted of the cold side of the PHE, a 275- W pump (P_2) and a 1.5- m^3 storage tank, with an overall heat transfer coefficient of $0.45 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ K}$. The thermal fluid was a 10% ethylenglycol solution in water, and the nominal flow rate was $m_{\text{fsec}} = 0.36 \text{ kg/s}$.
- The *tertiary circuit* included the aforementioned storage tank, a 110-W pump (P_3), an 11-kW ancillary fan-coil for heat rejection (heat sink), and the prototype generator. In the trials, P_3 pumped 10% ethylenglycol in water from the storage tank to the prototype generator at a mass flow rate of $m_{\text{fiter}} = 0.28\text{-kg/s}$.

Fig. 1. Solar-driven absorption cooling facility: schematic diagram.

2.2. Absorption chiller prototype

It is a directly air-cooled single effect LiBr–H₂O absorption chiller prototype with a nominal cooling capacity of 4.5-kW and 1- m^3 size. Built at the aforementioned Heat Pump Laboratory, the prototype is protected under a patent [30]. Its main components include a generator, a condenser, an evaporator, an absorber, a finned tube heat exchanger, hereafter FTHE, a heat regenerator, two solution pumps and a fan. In the heat regenerator (PHE), the LiBr–H₂O solution coming from the generator transfers heat to the LiBr–H₂O solution coming from the absorber. With this PHE two benefits are obtained. On the one hand, the higher the solution inlet temperature to the generator, the better the COP. On the other hand, the lower the inlet solution temperature to the absorber, the better the refrigerant absorption process is carried out [31].

A schematic diagram of the prototype is shown in Fig. 2.

The two main differences between this prototype and the market single effect absorption chillers are listed below.

- A *directly air-cooled system*: Nowadays, the LiBr–H₂O absorption chillers available in the market are water-cooled. This means that the absorption and condensation heats ($Q_a + Q_c$) are transferred to the outdoor air by means of a cooling tower. This prototype, however, transfers Q_a and Q_c to the outside air directly by forced convection.
- An *adiabatic flat-fan sheets absorber*. This device has been patented for its application in air-cooled and water-cooled absorption chillers [32]. In the absorber chamber only mass transfer takes place. Flat-fan sheets configurations were found to exhibit a mass transfer coefficient one order of magnitude

higher than both falling film (commonly used in commercial chillers) and spray absorbers [33]. From the absorber, the solution is pumped to the FTHE, where the absorption heat transfer (Q_a) is rejected to the outdoor air by forced convection, and next, returns to the absorber. The subcooling reached by the solution in the FTHE improves its affinity for the refrigerant vapour [34], which enhances the absorption process in the absorber.

Fig. 2. Prototype: schematic diagram.

The prototype was evaluated as a whole, and the results were obtained from the external fluids stand point.

The internal working fluid is a LiBr–H₂O solution with no additives, and the external fluids are the hot and chilled hydraulic circuits, and outdoor air.

- *Hot circuit:* the 10% ethylenglycol solution drawn from the storage tank (m_{fer}) enters the prototype generator at temperature t_{ig} . In the generator, it transfers Q_g to the solution, and lowers its temperature to t_{og} .
- *Chilled circuit:* a pump (P_4 , Fig. 1) drives the water to be chilled (m_{chill}) to the evaporator. There, Q_e is transferred to the refrigerant, lowering the temperature of the chilled water from t_{ie} to t_{oe} . The water is then pumped from the evaporator to the room to be air conditioned.
- *Outdoor air:* the air mass flow rate (m_{air}) cross flows, first through the FTHE and subsequently through the condenser. Throughout this process, the air temperature rises from t_{odb} to t_{oair} .

Fig. 3 shows the solar collector field, the storage tank and the directly air-cooled prototype.

Fig. 3. Solar collector field, storage tank and prototype.

3. Environmental variables

The solar-powered facility was tested on ten days in the summer of 2009.

The weather conditions prevailing on August 28, a particularly hot day, are discussed in section 3.1 below, while the most significant variables for each of the ten trial days are summarised in Section 3.2.

3.1. Hot day

The environmental variables considered were the solar irradiance on the tilted surface, G_t (Fig. 4) and t_{odb} (Fig. 5). These variables were recorded at a weather station that calculates the 10-min mean value for each variable from readings taken at 2-s intervals. Finally, the daily cooling load (Q_{cd}) calculated as described by Izquierdo et al. [25], is plotted in Fig. 6. The Q_{cd} peaked at 4.6 kW, and the cooling energy demand during working hours (9:00 AM–7:00 PM, solar time) was $E_{cd\ worktime} = 43.5$ kWh.

3.2. Trial period

Table 1 gives the daily solar irradiation on the tilted surface (H_t), the maximum and minimum outside dry bulb temperatures ($t_{odb\ max}$, $t_{odb\ min}$), total daily cooling energy demand ($E_{cd\ day}$) and $E_{cd\ worktime}$.

Day	H_t (kWh/m ²)	$t_{odb,max}$ (°C)	$t_{odb,min}$ (°C)	$E_{cd,day}$ (kWh)	$E_{cd,worktime}$ (kWh)
8/19/2009	7.5	37.6	31	69.4	44.3
8/20/2009	7.4	37.8	21.9	71.5	44.8
8/21/2009	7.5	37.2	18.3	57.9	42.9
8/26/2009	7.6	32.8	16.8	40.3	33.6
8/27/2009	7.6	35.3	18.6	47.7	38.8
8/28/2009	7.5	37.7	19.1	54.9	43.5
9/1/2009	6.2	34.2	21.8	59.6	40.8
9/2/2009	6.9	32.1	19.2	45.1	35.7
9/3/2009	7.6	35	14.4	63.2	49
9/4/2009	7.6	33.7	17.9	43.2	35.2
Total	73.4			552.8	408.6

Table 1.- Environmental variables and demand during the trial period

4. Process variables

The process variables studied were temperatures and flows. PT100-type calibrated thermal resistances were used, and minute-by-minute measurements were stored with a data acquisition system. The liquid flows were measured with ultrasonic flow meters, and the airflow was measured with an anemometer. The instrument accuracies are summarised in Table 2.

Device	Accuracy
PT100 sensors	$\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$
Data acquisition system	± 0.05 of the reading
Ultrasonic flow meter	$\pm 1-3\%$ of the reading
Anemometer	± 0.01 m/s

Table 2.- Instrument accuracies

Fig. 4. Solar irradiance on the tilted surface (28/08/2009)

Fig. 5. Outdoor dry bulb temperature (28/08/2009).

Fig. 6. Cooling load (28/08/2009)

5. Experimental procedure

P₁ started up when the collector plate temperature was 15°C higher than t_{odb} and turned off when it was 11°C higher. P₂ was triggered when t_{ocol} reached the target temperature, t_{tg} , i.e., when t_{ocol} was 7 °C higher than the temperature of the tank fluid in the P₂ discharge line, and shut down when it was 2°C higher. P₃ started up when the tank temperature in the pump suction line was 80°C or higher, and the room needed to be air conditioned; and turned off when one of these two conditions was not met.

6. Results

The findings for the hot day are discussed below, followed by a summary of the results for the entire ten days of the trial.

6.1. Hotday

The results obtained with the solar thermal plant, prototype and fancoil, are discussed below and followed by a description of solar facility performance (SFP), and the solar coefficient of performance (SCOP).

6.1.1. Solar thermal plant

Fig. 7 shows the collector inlet and outlet temperatures (t_{icol} , t_{ocol}) and the tank inlet and outlet temperatures from/to the secondary circuit (t_{itank} , t_{otank}). P₁ was operating at 8:00AM. m_{fcol} was pumped to the collectors, where its temperature was raised by G_t . At 8:50AM, the target temperature was reached ($t_{ocol} = t_{tg}$), triggering P₂ and initiating heat transfer to the storage tank. The insolation from sunrise to 8:50AM was needed to overcome thermal inertia in the system.

Fig. 7. Collectors inlet and outlet temperatures. Tank inlet and outlet temperatures (28/08/2009)

The highest collectors outlet temperature, $t_{ocol_max} = 113$ °C, was reached at 1:00 PM. Thereafter, t_{ocol} began to decline as a result of the decline in G_t . Heat transfer to the tank was finished when P₂ went off at 3:30PM. The highest t_{itank} attained was 107.3°C. The maximum difference between t_{ocol} and t_{icol} was 9.8°C, and between t_{icol} and t_{otank} was 8 °C. Fig. 8 shows the solar power on the tilted surface (Q_t) which peaked at 42.4 kW, the power transferred to the thermal fluid inside the collectors (Q_{col}) which reached 18.7 kW, and the power supplied to the storage tank (Q_{itank}) which exhibited a maximum value of 16.8 kW. The instantaneous values during the day were found with Eqs. (1)-(3).

$$Q_t = A_{col} G_t \quad (1)$$

$$Q_{col} = m_{fcol} C_{p_{fcol}} (t_{ocol} - t_{icol}) \quad (2)$$

$$Q_{itank} = m_{fsec} C_{p_{fsec}} (t_{otank} - t_{itank}) \quad (3)$$

The daily energy values were: $E_t = 316.7$ kWh, $E_{col} = 98.9$ kWh, and $E_{itank} = 86.2$ kWh.

Fig. 9 shows the collector efficiency (η_{col}) calculated from Eq. (4). The mean daily collector efficiency was 0.31.

$$\eta_{col} = \frac{Q_{col}}{Q_t} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 8. Thermal power values in the solar facility (28/08/2009)

Fig. 9. Collector efficiency (28/08/2009)

6.1.2. Absorption chiller prototype

The values obtained for the external fluids with the prototype are discussed below.

Flows m_{air} and m_{chill} remained approximately constant throughout the experiment, with values on the order of 0.28 kg/s. m_{air} , however, increased with rising t_{odb} , dissipating heat outdoors more effectively (Fig. 10).

Fig. 11 shows the inlet and outlet external fluid temperatures. At 9:00 AM, t_{odb} was 26.5 °C, and since the tank had reached a temperature of 90 °C, heat was being transferred to the prototype generator. From that time until 3:10 PM, t_{odb} rose to 37.7 °C and t_{ig} to 106 °C, as a result of the heat transferred from the solar field to the tank. The evaporator outlet water temperature (t_{oe}), in turn, declined from 25 to 15.5 °C between 9:00 AM and 10:40 AM, after which it remained constant at around 16 °C until 3:10 PM. This was possible because of the high t_{ig} temperatures reached as t_{odb} increased. These results compare favourably with findings reported by Izquierdo et al. (25) for a commercial indirectly air-cooled chiller using thermal oil as a heat source: in that facility, when t_{odb} was 28.6–38 °C and t_{ig} was 94.5–105 °C, t_{oe} rose from 17.3 to 20.5 °C.

After 3:30 PM, although t_{odb} was still over 37 °C, t_{ig} began to decline when the storage tank ceased to receive heat from the collectors while nonetheless continuing to transfer heat to the generator. This decline in feed temperature led to a rise in t_{oe} until the prototype shut down. The difference between t_{odb} and t_{air} held steady at around 5–6 °C throughout the trial.

The values of Q_g , Q_e and Q_{a+c} calculated from Eqs. (5)-(7) are plotted in Fig. 12.

$$Q_g = m_{f\text{ter}} C_{p\text{f\text{ter}}} (t_{ig} - t_{og}) \quad (5)$$

$$Q_e = m_{\text{chill}} C_{p\text{w}} (t_{ie} - t_{oe}) \quad (6)$$

$$Q_{a+c} = m_{\text{air}} C_{p\text{air}} (t_{\text{air}} - t_{\text{odb}}) \quad (7)$$

Fig. 10. External fluid flows for the prototype (28/08/2009)

Fig. 11. Inlet and outlet external fluid temperatures for the prototype (28/08/2009)

Fig. 12. Heat transfer rate in the generator, evaporator and absorber-condenser assembly (28/08/2009)

Heat began to be transferred to the generator at 9:10AM. Q_g rose from 9:10 to 11:00AM and held fairly constant at around 6.5 kW until 3:00 PM. The prototype began to produce cold at approximately 9:20AM and Q_c rose until 12:00 noon. From noon to 3:10 PM, while t_{odb} ranged from 35 to 37.7°C, Q_c remained flat at a value of approximately 4.3 kW. After 3:10 PM, Q_c declined due to the downturn in t_{ig} as a result of the inability of the solar facility to produce high t_{ig} values after that time. Heat ceased to be transferred to the generator at 4:20 PM, and the system ceased to produce cold at 4:40PM. The total heat supplied to the generator was $E_g = 40.1$ kWh, and the daily cold produced by the prototype was $E_c = 25.1$ kWh. The heat transferred to the outdoor air by the absorber and the condenser was $E_{a+c} = 64.3$ kWh. Between 10:00AM and 3:00PM, the solar-powered air-conditioning facility covered laboratory demand. The solar fraction (SF) defined as the ratio between E_e and E_{cd} , in per cent, came to 57.7% during the working hours.

Fig. 13 shows the thermal, electric, and primary energy COPs, calculated from Eqs. (8)-(10), respectively.

$$COP_{th} = \frac{Q_c}{Q_g} \quad (8)$$

$$COP_{elec} = \frac{Q_c}{W_{elec_prot}} \quad (9)$$

$$COP_{prim_energy} = \frac{Q_c}{Q_g + (W_{elec_prot}/\eta_{conv})} \quad (10)$$

Fig. 13. COP_{th} , COP_{elec} , COP_{prim_energy} (28/08/2009)

The mean daily COP_{th} , calculated from the ratio between E_e and E_g , was 0.62. This result compares favourably with the findings reported by Izquierdo et al. (25) for a commercial indirectly air-cooled absorption chiller. In Eq. (9), W_{elec_prot} includes the electric power of the chilled water circulation pump, absorber-generator solution pump, absorber-FTHE solution pump and fan, which amounted to a total of 700W. The daily electricity consumption of the prototype was 4.8 kWh, and the mean daily COP_{elec} was 5.2. This value is higher than the COP_{elec} listed in catalogues for comparable residential air-cooled mechanical compression chillers. Finally, in Eq. (10), η_{conv} represents the mean performance in a country's steam power plants in terms of the conversion of primary energy to electric power. In Spain, $\eta_{conv} = 0.38$ (35). That translated into daily primary energy consumption of the ancillary equipment in the prototype of 12.6 kWh, and a mean daily COP_{prim_energy} of 0.48.

6.1.3. Fan coil

Fig. 14 shows the inlet (t_{i0}) and outlet (t_{orc}) air temperatures. The initial t_{i0} was 27.1 °C, which, after declining to around 25°C, remained within the range of temperatures established by the Spanish Regulations for Thermal Facilities in Buildings (29) throughout the trial (10:15AM-4:15 PM).

Fig. 14. Fan coil: inlet and outlet air temperatures (28/08/2009)

6.1.4. Solar facility performance and solar coefficient of performance

Fig. 15 shows both SFP and SCOP, calculated from Eqs. (11) and (12), respectively.

$$\text{SFP} = \frac{Q_g}{Q_t} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{SCOP} = \frac{Q_e}{Q_t} \quad (12)$$

Fig. 15. Solar facility performance and solar coefficient of performance (28/08/2009)

The mean daily SFP and SCOP were 0.13 and 0.08, respectively. Despite the presence of Gt, from 5:40 to approximately 9:00 AM, and from 4:40 to 7:20PM, no heat was transferred to the generator or cold produced in the evaporator. This explains why the mean daily SFP and SCOP were lower than the values recorded while the prototype was in operation.

Finally, Table 3 lists the range of uncertainty for the indirect variables, calculated from the Kline and McClintock equation (36).

Indirect variable	Unity	Uncertain
Q_t	kW	± 0.4
Q_{col}	kW	± 0.3
Q_{itank}	kW	± 0.3
Q_g	kW	± 0.2
Q_e	kW	± 0.2
η_{col}	-	± 0.01
COP_{th}	-	± 0.03
SFP	-	± 0.004
SCOP	-	± 0.004

Table 3.- Instrument accuracies

6.2. Trial/ period

The daily high t_{ocol} values ranged from 107 to 116 °C, and the peak daily t_{ig} from 96 to 109 °C. Despite the high temperatures feeding into the generator, no solution crystallized inside the prototype. By way of comparison, the only similar commercial chiller ever marketed (although the model in question used an indirectly air-cooled system) had an operating ceiling of 105 °C. For reasons of safety, it would not operate at higher temperatures [25]. The lowest t_{oe} attained by the prototype was 14.3°C, at $t_{odb}=30^\circ\text{C}$ and $t_{ig}=100^\circ\text{C}$. The electric power consumed by P_1 , P_2 , P_3 and the prototype came to 98 kWh, equivalent to 257.9 kWh of primary energy. Table 4 summarises the energy values in the solar facility and the prototype, and Table 5 gives the SF, and the mean η_{col} , SFP, thermal and electrical COPs. and SCOP values for the trial period. When the primary energy consumed by the ancillary equipment was taken into consideration, the mean SFP, COP and SCOP came to 0.11, 0.39 and 0.057. respectively.

Date	E_t (kWh)	E_{col} (kWh)	E_{itank} (kWh)	E_g (kWh)	E_e (kWh)	$E_{elec.P1}$ (kWh)	$E_{elec.P2}$ (kWh)	$E_{elec.P3}$ (kWh)	$E_{elec.pr}$ (kWh) _{ot}
8/19/2009	315.9	77.8	67.4	35.5	18.2	3.4	1.2	0.5	4.7
8/20/2009	311.4	97	82	42.7	18.3	3.1	1.1	0.5	4.9
8/21/2009	318.1	99.2	83.8	35	19.6	3.2	1.1	0.7	4.8
8/26/2009	319	67.2	59.3	36.5	20.2	3.1	1.1	0.7	4.5
8/27/2009	318.9	96.1	87.7	41.5	23.2	3.3	1.2	0.7	4.0
8/28/2009	316.7	98.9	86.2	40.1	25.1	3.3	1.1	0.8	4.8
9/1/2009	261.6	65.2	58.2	26.5	13.4	3.2	1.1	0.8	4.7
9/2/2009	290.7	71.4	64.1	22.1	13.8	3.1	1.1	0.7	5.3
9/3/2009	321.8	90.3	80.6	41.1	22	3.2	1.1	0.8	5.1
9/4/2009	321.5	87.4	78.4	41.5	18.4	3.2	1.1	0.8	4.8
Total	3095.6	850.5	747.7	362.5	192.2	32.1	11.2	7.0	47.6

Table 4.- Trial period energy values

SF(%) working hours	η_{col}	COP_{th}	COP_{elec}	SFP	SCOP
47	0.27	0.53	4.04	0.12	0.062

Table 5.- Solar fraction, mean collector efficiency, COP_{th} , COP_{elec} , SFP and SCOP for the trial period

7. Conclusions

The solar-powered cooling facility tested here consisted of a vacuum flat-plate collector field and an innovate directly air-cooled, 4.5-kW, single effect, LiBr-H₂O prototype absorption chiller. connected to a fan coil to air condition a 40-m² room. The conclusions drawn from the findings are listed below.

- The solar field comprised 24 vacuum flat-plate collectors with a total aperture area of 42.2 m², i.e., 9 m² of aperture area per kW of refrigeration. This value is higher than found on the European market and higher than suggested in some publications.
- With these vacuum flat-plate collectors, the peak t_{ocol} recorded ranged from 107 to 116°C, while mean collector performance (ten days) came to $r_{i,01}=0.27$. Using these collectors for this type of applications lowers investment costs. compared to vacuum tube solar collectors.
- Despite the high temperatures (109 °C) of the fluid fed by the solar

- facility into the prototype generator. no LiBr-H₂O crystallization was observed. The maximum inlet temperature allowed in the generator was higher than found in standard market air-cooled chillers of similar characteristics.
- On days when $t_{odb} = 30^{\circ}\text{C}$. the water was cooled to 14.3°C . The days when the high t_{odb} was 35°C . the prototype operated at around its rated capacity. On days when t_{odb} was around 38°C , Q_e was 4.2 kW , t_{oe} remained at around 16°C , and t_{obd} at around 25°C , a value compliant with the Spanish Regulations for thermal facilities in buildings in effect in 2009.
- During the trial period (ten days), the mean SFP was 0.12; the mean COP_{th} , 0.53; and the mean SCOP, 0.06. Deducting the electric power consumed by the facility would bring these values down. in terms of primary energy, by 8.3%, 26.4% and 8%, respectively. Finally, the SF found for the entire trial period was 47%.
- In conclusion, while no air-cooled LiBr-H₂O absorption chillers are presently on the market, the results obtained with this directly air-cooled prototype are indicative of the potential for using this technology in residential buildings in the future. Further tests are presently being conducted on the prototype to improve its performance.

Nomenclature

A	area (m ²)
COP	coefficient of performance (-)
C _p	specific heat (J/kg°C)
E	energy (kWh)
G	solar irradiance (W/m ²)
H	daily solar irradiance (kWh/m ²)
m	mass flow (kg/s)
Q	heat transfer rate (kW)
SCOP	solar coefficient of performance (-)
SF	solar fraction (%)
SFP	solar facility performance (-)
t	temperature (°C)
W	electric power (kW)

Subscripts

a	absorber
a+c	absorber and condenser
c	condenser
col	collector
conv	conversion
chill	chilling
cd	cooling demand
e	evaporator
elec	electric
fc _{ol}	collector fluid
fs _{ec}	secondary circuit fluid
ft _{er}	tertiary circuit fluid
g	generator
ic _{ol}	collector inlet
ie	evaporator inlet
ig	generator inlet
in	indoor
it _{ank}	tank inlet (from secondary circuit)
max	maximum
min	minimum
o _{air}	air outlet
o _{col}	collector outlet
o _{db}	outdoor dry bulb
o _e	evaporator outlet

ofc	fan coil outlet
og	generator outlet
otank	tank outlet (to secondary circuit)
prot	prototype
t	tilted
tg	target
th	thermal
tank	storage tank
w	water

Greek alphabet

η efficiency

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